

1 Exposure of human cells to elacestrant results in activation of BRCA1 and the stem loop binding protein,
2 SLBP.

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7 Elecestrant was recently approved by the FDA for treatment of breast cancer in humans containing an
8 ESR1 mutation. We measured total transcription by RNA sequencing in human breast cancer cells treated
9 with the endocrine therapy (ET) agent elecestrant. We demonstrate here that despite effective hormone
10 deprivation, the first-in-class selective estrogen receptor degrader (SERD) activated *BRCA1* and the stem
11 loop binding *SLBP*. Cells treated with elecestrant featured Rad51 activation concomitant with induction of
12 H2AX. Systems biologic approaches focused on describing all cellular transactions using transcriptomics
13 illustrate novel aspects of signaling associated with mechanism of action for a selective estrogen receptor
14 degrader.

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